

CULTURE OF THE PEOPLE OF CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotation: The countries of Central Asia consist of independent states of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan with similar nationalities and religions. We will study the purpose and relevance of the traditions and customs of these countries of Central Asia.

Key words: "Great Silk" road, SSR, Sughd, Parthia, Choch, Bactria, Margyona.

The culture of Central Asia occupies an important place in the history of world culture. The whole world has already appreciated its medieval culture. Even the ancient culture of the peoples of Bactria, Margiyona, Sughd, Parthia, Fergana, Khorezm, and Choch amazes the world. Although the study of the ancient culture of the Central Asian region began decades ago, researchers were surprised by the uniqueness and rich content of this culture. The culture of Central Asia combines the great cultural elements of the West and the East and acquires its own individuality, which becomes the basis for further development. I.A. As Karimov said, "Since a nation that knows its history and derives spiritual strength from it cannot be defeated, we must restore our true history, arm our people, our nation with this history. It is necessary to arm with history, to arm once again". When determining the conditions for the emergence of the culture of the peoples of Central Asia, it is necessary to first pay attention to its geographical location and natural resources. Cultural studies pays special attention to the importance of landscape, climate, and biosphere factors in the formation of any culture. The

nature of the Central Asian region is very diverse. Here, fertile valleys and oases, muddy rivers, rugged deserts, steppe hills, and the high mountains of Pamir and Tangritog are side by side. This feature created an opportunity for the formation of farming, herding, mountain tribes and peoples' economic style and unique cultures. The pamphlet entitled "Ancient Civilization" shows two features of the culture of Central Asia: on the one hand, the interaction of different cultures, and on the other hand, its development in close contact with other centers of ancient civilizations. If we observe these features in detail, the processes of formation of the culture of Central Asia will be clearly manifested. The "Great Silk Road" was of great importance in the development of the oldest culture of these countries. This trade route caused cultural exchange and development. The differences in the living conditions of the people living in the fertile valleys, deserts and steppes of Central Asia, the early appearance of different farms led to the formation of unique cultures. This process took place on the basis of close military relations, and thanks to the economic and cultural relations of the tribes and peoples, development began earlier. From the earliest times, the exchange of products between farming, animal husbandry and mountain hunting tribes was of great importance in the economy of the peoples of Central Asia, and it was preserved for a long time. Along with the differences in lifestyle and economic activity, the ethnic and linguistic proximity of the peoples of the region has been very harmoniously recorded in ancient Greek and Chinese sources. The strong economic relations, ethnic and linguistic unity of the peoples of Central Asia did not allow them to live separately from each other. As a result, among the classical culture of the ancient East, the ancient culture of Central Asia is distinguished and formed in its own way. Initially, two different cultures are mixed in this culture: the world of nomadism and primitiveness and the world of civilization; Here, the idea of "uniqueness" is being formed, which has reflected the interaction of cultures typical of ancient cultures. Despite the many differences between the

sedentary farming and nomadic peoples of Central Asia, close relations have existed since before. ``installed.

The commonality of religious beliefs, traditions, folklore, and moral standards has led to the formation of a cultural commonality. Therefore, it is permissible to dwell on the existence of various subcultures that make up the integrated culture of Central Asia: the subculture of the ancient states (Bactria, Sughd, Khorezm, Fergana, Margiyona), steppe nomads-Sak, massaget , Da-Kochchi subculture, subculture of Pamir and Tangritog tribes. The second aspect of the uniqueness of the culture of Central Asia is related to the very convenient geographical location of the region. The region is directly bordered by three great Eastern civilizations, such as Mesopotamia, India and China, and developed in contact with the fifth Western civilization - Greece and Rome. Due to the inevitability of such relations, the culture of Central Asia has become a mediator between the East and the West. performed the task of `prik. In particular, through the territory of Central Asia, Buddhism spread to the whole world, the manifestations of Hellenistic culture were transferred to India and China, and in the exchange of cultural wealth (knowledge, religious ideas, discoveries, religious works) from East to West and from West to East, the Central Differences in the living conditions of the people living in the fertile valleys, deserts and steppes of Orcasian Asia, the earlier appearance of different farms led to the formation of unique cultures.

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Central Asia refers to the five Muslim republics that gained independence after the collapse of the Soviet Union: Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. During the Soviet period, the term "Central Asia"

and "Kazakhstan" was applied to this region. However, after gaining independence in 1991, both these countries and foreign countries began to use the term Central Asia. In 1992, the leaders of five countries adopted the term Central Asia at an official meeting. Currently, this term is accepted by the world community. Central Asian departments have been opened in most international organizations and research institutes. However, from a geographical point of view, Central Asia also includes Afghanistan, Mongolia, and the Uighur regions of China. There is also the term Greater Central Asia. Some politicians and researchers add Iran, Azerbaijan, Turkey, and even some parts of India to this area.

At the level of Central Asia, there are also regional cooperation efforts in a certain sense. The Central Asian Cooperation Organization can be cited as an example of these actions. However, until now, there has been no certain regularity and continuity in such actions. Culture There are different cultural centers, views and traditions in these countries. Uzbekistan alone has various customs and traditions, such as Sunnat weddings, Nikoh weddings, Aqiqah weddings, Prophet's age weddings, Fatiha weddings, etc. there is.

This ceremony traditions also exist in Kazakhstan, one of their interesting traditions is the ceremony of stealing a girl. If the groom steals the girl before the wedding, the family members have to give this girl to that boy. they did.

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